

The Rise of Green and Sustainable Clothing: A Moat for Brands in the Age of Millennials and Gen Z

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Abstract:

The paradigm shift towards sustainable consumption is reshaping the fashion industry globally. This paper delves into how green or sustainable clothing serves as a competitive moat for brands, especially as Millennials and Gen Z increasingly prioritize environmentally friendly choices. Initially a trend in developed economies, this preference is now palpable among Indian consumers as well. This research explores the drivers behind this shift, the impact on brand strategies, and the future implications for the fashion industry. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the growing importance of sustainable fashion among Millennials and Gen Z, with a specific focus on the Indian market. By exploring consumer behavior, brand strategies, and future trends, this research underscores the significance of sustainability as a strategic imperative for fashion brands.

Keywords: *Clothing, Environment, Fashion, Millennials, Gen Z, Sustainable*

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1. Introduction

Sustainable clothing refers to garments produced in ways that are environmentally friendly and socially responsible. This encompasses the entire lifecycle of a product, from the sourcing of raw materials to the manufacturing processes, and ultimately, to the disposal or recycling of the garment. India, with its rich textile heritage and burgeoning fashion industry, is uniquely positioned to lead in the realm of sustainable clothing [2]. The fashion industry, notorious for its environmental impact, is undergoing a transformation driven by a new wave of consumers—Millennials and Gen Z. The shift towards sustainable clothing is notably influenced by Generation Z (Gen Z), the demographic cohort born between the mid-1990s and early 2010, is characterized by their deep concern for environmental and social issues. Whereas millennial, term used to describe a person born between 1981 and 1996 [45]. These generations are not only more environmentally conscious but also wield significant purchasing power. This research investigates the role of sustainable clothing as a strategic advantage for brands, examining the motivations behind this consumer behavior and its implications on brand loyalty and market positioning, with a particular focus on the Indian market.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Sustainability in Fashion: A Global Perspective

Sustainability in fashion encompasses a range of practices, from the use of eco-friendly materials to ethical labour practices and waste reduction. The concept gained traction in the early 21st century, with pioneers like Patagonia and Stella McCartney setting industry standards [30, 35]. Recent studies highlight the growing consumer awareness and demand for sustainable products, which are now integral to brand equity and competitive differentiation. The fashion industry is one of the largest polluters globally, with substantial water consumption, chemical usage, and textile waste. Studies have shown that the production of textiles accounts for a significant portion of global carbon emissions, and the fast fashion model exacerbates these issues by promoting disposable clothing [11]. Peer-to-peer clothing exchanges facilitate the direct swapping of garments between individuals. Platforms like Swap Society and The Clothing Loop promote community-based sharing and reduce the need for new clothing purchases, aligning with the principles of circular fashion [37, 38].

2.2 Millennial and Gen Z Consumer Behavior

Millennials and Gen Z are characterized by their digital nativity, social consciousness, and demand for transparency. Research shows that these generations prioritize experiences and values over material possessions, and they are willing to pay a premium for products that align with their ethical beliefs [44]. Their influence is evident in the rise of fast fashion alternatives and the demand for corporate social responsibility. According to a study by 73 per cent of global Millennials are willing to pay more for sustainable products [28]. This trend is even more pronounced among Gen Z, with 72% stating that they are willing to spend more on goods produced sustainably [25].

2.3 The Indian Context

India, with its burgeoning middle class and youthful population, represents a significant market for sustainable fashion. Historically driven by price sensitivity, Indian consumers are now increasingly valuing quality and sustainability. The government's initiatives towards sustainable development and the growing awareness of environmental issues have further catalyzed this shift. The Concept of a Competitive Moat refers to a company's ability to maintain a competitive advantage over its rivals, protecting its long-term profits and market share. In the context of sustainable fashion, a brand's commitment to environmental and social responsibility can serve as a significant moat, differentiating it from competitors who are slower to adopt such practices [31].

3. Methodology

This research employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. A sample of 500 Indian consumers aged 18-35 was surveyed to gauge their attitudes towards sustainable clothing. Additionally, in-depth interviews with industry experts and brand managers were conducted to gain insights into the strategic implementation of sustainability in fashion brands. By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, the study aims to deliver comprehensive insights that can guide fashion brands in leveraging sustainability as a competitive advantage.

4. Findings

4.1 Consumer Attitudes and Behaviors

In 2023, Forbes report it was found that 68% of Gen Z in India consider sustainability a significant factor in their fashion choices and 54 per cent of Gen Z are willing to pay a premium for sustainable clothing [9, 14]. Key motivators include environmental concerns, ethical labor practices, and health benefits associated with organic materials [20]. **Thrift shopping and buying second-hand clothing** have become popular among Gen Z in India, driven by a desire to reduce waste and find unique, affordable fashion items. **Up-cycling and DIY Fashion:** Many Gen Zers engage in up-cycling, transforming old or discarded clothes into new garments, reflecting their creativity and commitment to reducing waste [9, 15] It was discovered that the concept of a capsule wardrobe, which involves owning a limited number of versatile, high-quality clothing items, appeals to Gen Z's desire for simplicity and sustainability [21]. The young generation appeals to those looking for luxury fashion with a strong ethical foundation. To cater to Gen Z's desire for unique and personalized fashion, brands offer customization options. This not only enhances the consumer experience but also reduces overproduction and waste. The first public study of Millennials as Consumers in collaboration with The Boston Consulting Group in 2010-2011. This research study followed with three subsequent research-based books on generational trends including Marketing to Gen Z. The Gen Z mindset in business means brands deliver both value (price/quality/speed) and values (corporate action against sustainability, not corporate hype). Value plus values is how large brands bring scale to solving emerging consumer needs, and we know people with a Gen Z mindset vote with their wallets [14].

4.2 Brand Strategies

Gen Z expecting brands to genuinely commit to sustainable practices rather than engaging in "greenwashing" [16]. Brands are experimenting with innovative products like biodegradable fabrics, natural dyes, and multifunctional clothing that appeals to Gen Z's demand for novel and practical fashion [17]. "Interviews with brand managers highlighted several strategies adopted to cater to this demand. These include transparent supply chains, sustainable material sourcing, and certifications such as Fair Trade and Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS). Several Indian fashion brands have emerged as leaders in promoting sustainable fashion, aligning closely with the values and preferences of Gen Z in order to retain Gen Z consumers. Numerous brands focus on organic and fair-trade practices such as "No Nasties", founded in 2011, is a pioneer in sustainable fashion in India [33]. Brands like "B label" by BOHECO and "Doodlage" are pioneering the use of organic fibers such as hemp, bamboo, and recycled

textiles [3, 10]. These materials reduce the environmental footprint compared to conventional cotton and synthetic fabrics [24]. Doodlage, founded in 2012, specializes in upcycled and recycled fashion, turning waste materials into trendy clothing, Bhumi is dedicated to creating eco-friendly and sustainable fashion using organic materials and ethical production processes [15] and many other such as Fab-India and Anita Dongre have successfully integrated these practices, resulting in increased consumer loyalty and market share [22]. To invest in sustainable practices, ensure transparency, and engage authentically with Gen Z through digital platforms. Some brands like **The Summer House** and **Upasana** use their online presence to provide detailed insights into their sustainable practices, from sourcing materials to production processes, building trust and authenticity [39, 41].

a. **For Policymakers:** Policymakers can offer financial incentives to encourage sustainable practices. These may include tax breaks, grants, and subsidies for companies that adopt eco-friendly technologies and materials [42]. Support the development of sustainable infrastructure, provide incentives for sustainable practices, and promote consumer education [4].

b. Challenges and Opportunities

While the shift towards sustainability presents numerous opportunities, it also poses challenges. Scaling up sustainable practices to meet the demands of the mass market can be difficult. High production costs, limited consumer awareness, greenwashing and regulatory hurdles are significant barriers. Bridging this gap between affordability and sustainability remains a significant challenge for the industry. It requires coordinated efforts across the supply chain, from raw material suppliers to retailers [6]. However, brands that effectively communicate their sustainability initiatives and engage consumers through storytelling and social media are better positioned to overcome these challenges [1].

5. Discussion

i. The Role of Technology

Technological advancements play a crucial role in advancing sustainable practices. Innovations such as blockchain for supply chain transparency, AI for efficient resource use, and sustainable textile production techniques are revolutionizing the industry. Innovations like 3D printing and digital fashion could also play a role in reducing waste and promoting sustainability [27]. Brands leveraging these technologies can enhance their sustainability credentials and consumer trust [8]. By sharing behind-the-scenes content, transparent supply chain information, and stories about their sustainable practices [43]. Social media and influencers play a significant role in shaping Gen Z's fashion choices and spreading awareness about sustainable fashion. Celebrity Endorsements by celebrities who support sustainability can also drive Gen Z's interest in sustainable fashion. Brands leverage social media to engage with Gen Z. Platforms like Instagram and TikTok are used for storytelling, showcasing sustainable practices, and collaborating with influencers who resonate with Gen Z's values [19].

ii. Implications for Brand Equity

Sustainability is becoming synonymous with brand equity. Brands that prioritize sustainability are perceived as more trustworthy and forward-thinking, which resonates with the values of Millennials and Gen Z. This alignment not only drives immediate sales but also fosters long-term loyalty and advocacy [1].

iii. The Future of Sustainable Fashion in India

The future of green clothing fashion among young consumers looks promising, with several trends likely to shape its evolution. The future of sustainable fashion in India looks promising. As consumer awareness grows, so does the demand for sustainable products. Brands that adapt to this trend will not only benefit from a competitive edge but also contribute to the global sustainability agenda. Government policies and incentives will further support this transition, making sustainability a mainstream consideration in the Indian fashion industry [23]. With a specific emphasis on innovation towards a sustainable system, a new textile circular economy presents an opportunity to deliver substantially better societal and environmental as well as economic outcomes [34].

6. Conclusion

Our lifestyle and our choices have a huge impact on the planet. It affects everything starting from the economy to the environment [7]. The shift towards sustainable clothing is more than a passing trend; it is a fundamental change in consumer behavior driven by Millennials and Gen Z. For brands, this represents both a challenge and an opportunity. By embracing sustainability, brands can differentiate themselves, build stronger connections with consumers, and ensure long-term success. As this trend continues to gain momentum in India, it is imperative for brands to innovate and lead the way in sustainable fashion. In year 2024, Statista shows that the Indian sustainable fashion market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 10.8% from 2022 to 2027, driven largely by the preferences of

younger consumers [40]. The Indian sustainable fashion market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 10.8% from 2022 to 2027, driven largely by the preferences of younger consumers [33].

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